

SULPHUR DICHLORIDE AS A CHLORINATING AGENT

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Sulphur monochloride is known to act as a chlorinating agent. It reacts with a number of metals and metalloids, producing corresponding metal chlorides (Domanicki, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 48, 1724; Nicolardot, *Compt. rend.*, 1908, 147, 1304). Excess of sulphur monochloride rapidly attacks metallic tellurium at ordinary temperature, producing tellurium tetrachloride (Lenher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 188). However, only a few references, which attest to the utility of sulphur dichloride as a chlorinating agent, have been recorded in literature (Korshak *et al.*, *J. Gen. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1947, 17, 1626; Dumas, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1832, 49, 204).

These investigations, referred to above, relate to the study of the chlorinating effect of sulphur dichloride on some metals and present a novel method for the rapid synthesis of selenium and tellurium tetrachlorides. Elementary tellurium reacts instantaneously with sulphur dichloride, producing crystalline tellurium tetrachloride. The reaction is highly exothermic. The filtrate, obtained on separation of the product, on fractionation afforded a fraction which distilled at 137-39°, showing the formation of sulphur monochloride as a product of the reaction. (Found: Te, 47.59; Cl, 52.16. Calc. for TeCl₄: Te, 47.36; Cl, 52.64%).

Selenium also, when treated with an excess of sulphur dichloride, is immediately transformed into the tetrachloride in an exothermic reaction, sulphur monochloride being produced at the same time. (Found: Se, 35.30; Cl, 64.63. Calc. for SeCl₄: Se, 35.75; Cl, 64.25%).

The action of excess of sulphur dichloride on metallic tin results in the immediate dissolution of the metal, forming stannic chloride. A large amount of heat is evolved. The separation of stannic chloride from sulphur dichloride and sulphur monochloride, a product of reaction, by fractional distillation was, however, not found to be practicable as always a mixture of stannic chloride and sulphur monochloride distilled over. The formation of stannic chloride was established by adding to the reaction mixture a solution of dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride in sulphur dichloride, when immediately a crystalline complex of the formula [(CH₃)₂N.C₆H₅.C₇H₇]₂SnCl₄. $\frac{1}{2}$ SCl₂ separated out. Formation of crystalline complexes of the formula [(CH₃)₂N.C₆H₅.C₇H₇]₂SnCl₄ has been established beyond doubt in benzoyl chloride (Paul and Singh, *Curr. Sci.*, 1957, 28, 391) and acetyl chloride (Paul and Sandhu, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 262). (Found: Sn, 14.69; Cl, 29.97; N, 3.46; S, 1.86. [(CH₃)₂N.C₆H₅.C₇H₇]₂SnCl₄. $\frac{1}{2}$ SCl₂ requires Sn, 14.71; Cl, 30.79; N, 3.47; S, 1.98%).

All these reactions can be represented by the general equation:

This mechanism is supported by an early observation that sulphur dichloride dissociates into sulphur monochloride and chlorine (Michaelis and Schifferdecker, *Ber.*, 1873, 6, 995):

and also from the well-known reaction:

which is used to remove the small amount of sulphur dichloride that may be present as an impurity in sulphur monochloride.

Metallic mercury on being added to an excess of sulphur dichloride immediately solidifies into a black mass. On trituration a highly exothermic reaction takes place and mercuric chloride is formed. (Found: Hg, 74.01; Cl, 25.85. Calc. for HgCl_2 : Hg, 73.85; Cl, 26.15%).

Powdered antimony metal rapidly reacts with an excess of sulphur dichloride and goes into solution. A large amount of heat is produced and in a few moments a yellow fluffy precipitate settles down at the bottom of the reaction vessel. Due to its hygroscopic nature, the product could not be analysed quantitatively, but qualitative tests showed the presence of Sb^{III} , chlorine and sulphur. Probably, it is a solvate of antimony trichloride with sulphur monochloride.

Arsenic metal, in a similar way, reacted instantaneously with excess of sulphur dichloride and went into solution, forming arsenic trichloride. Due to the reasons given in the case of stannic chloride, the separation of arsenic trichloride in pure form was also found to be difficult. Its formation was established by allowing it to react with dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride in sulphur dichloride solution, when an orange-coloured complex separated which was highly hygroscopic and could not be analysed quantitatively. Qualitative tests, however, showed the presence of As^{III} , chlorine, nitrogen and sulphur.

Metals like zinc, iron and cadmium have not been found to react with sulphur dichloride easily. A similar behaviour of these metals has also been found in the case of sulphur monochloride (Domanicki, *loc. cit.*).

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